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Influence Of Social Demands On Students’ Behavioural Patterns And Academic Achievement In Universities In North-Central, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the Influence of Social Demands on Students’ Behavioural Patterns and Academic Achievement in the Universities in North-central, Nigeria. Four objectives, four research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The research design were descriptive survey and ex-post facto. The population of the study was 25,115 students and 394 were randomly sampled using 5% of Yamane table of sample size (1967). The instrument used was a self-structured questionnaire titled: “Social Demands Questionnaire” (SDQ). The instrument was validated through expert assessment of face, content and construct. The instrument was pilot tested using two hundred level students of University of Abuja, Faculty of Education. The reliability was determined using test re-test method and the results of the two administrations were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC) which yielded a reliability index of 0.71 and was considered reliable for the study. The copies of the instrument were administered and 394 were sieved based on code. The collected data were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages for demographic data. While mean scores and standard deviation were used to answers the research questions. The hypotheses 1 to 2 were tested using t-test. While hypothesis three was tested using ANOVA. Findings revealed that there were negative social demands in the Universities such as substance abuse, stealing, and many others. It was further revealed that, students academic achievement were within average. Results from the tested hypotheses revealed that Federal and State Universities students did not differ significantly in the influence of social demands as regards to substance abuse, stealing, and many others. While students’ academic achievement were within average irrespective of gender. It was also found that, male students were more victims of nrgative social demands. It was therefore, recommended that Guidance counsellors, parents, teachers, religious bodies and other stakeholders should organize gender based programme both in Federal and State Universities to discuss the influence of negative social demands in relation to students’ behavioural patterns and academic achievement in Universities.

Keywords:

INTRODUCTION

In contemporary educational environments, the interplay between social demands and its profound influence on students' behavioural patterns and academic achievement cannot be over emphasized. As students transition into university life, they encounter a myriad of social influences that can shape their experiences, choices, and ultimately, their academic outcomes. Universities serve as microcosms of society, where diverse groups of individuals converge with varying values, beliefs, and behaviours.

Furthermore, tertiary institutions, particularly universities, play critical roles in shaping the lives and future of countless young individuals. These institutions are not only center for academic learning but also center for social model where students interact, form relationships, and experience various social demands and influences. Over the years, the impact of social demands on students within these institutions have gained increasing attention from educators, researchers and policymakers (Susanne, Mike & Norbert 2021). Conceptually, social demands refer to a combined pressure that challenges an individual in everyday life such as social construct and economic pressure (Gibson, 2019). On the other hand, academic achievement refers to how well a student is accomplishing his or her tasks and studies. More so, it is the ability to study and remember facts and being able to communicate one's knowledge verbally or in writing (Okorie, 2018). According to Narad and Abdullahi (2016), academic achievement refers to knowledge gained which is assessed by marks given by a teacher and other extracurricular activities over a specific period or session. In addition, academic achievement is a measure of how well a student performs cumulatively in an academic environment.

However, these social demands may significantly influence behavioural patterns and contribute to students' negative social behaviour like cultism, indecent dressing, stealing and substance abuse. More importantly, the period of University education represents a critical developmental period in the lives of students both socially, psychologically and academically. This is because, it is the period when students may be exposed to many social constructs like substance abuse, cultism and clubbing which may influence their behavioural patterns negatively (Susanne, Mike & Norbert 2021). They added that, social construct are ideas, concept and perception that is created and widely accepted within a group or setting. It is also a powerful force that influences perceptions, interactions and behaviours negatively.

In addition, some of these social influences or demands could be regarded as social life styles such as cult activities, romantic relationships, smoking and involvement in club activities (Gibson, 2019). The author asserted that these demands tend to affect behavioural patterns as well as pressurize students to channel their energy into the wrong direction like clubs, birthday parties and other social gatherings. Other social demands according to Liotsiou, Halford and Moreau (2016) were chatting on none educational issues, watching videos online and lack of effective sleep at night due to these activities. They further stressed that most students who are influenced by these social demands like online video usually skip classes, do not do their assignments and other academic responsibilities. However, University in this study cut across State University and Federal University respectively, and the social demands within these institution may differ from one another.

However, the society demands that the youths or students should present good conduct and norms which are acceptable to the general community while in school. This is why several schools have rules and regulations that guide students' conduct. In the opinion of Omollo, and Yambo (2017), no decent society would like its youths to be recalcitrant to its laid down values and accepted norms. They further stressed that youngsters or students are seen as a group constantly abusing independence while in school and this tends to influence their behavioural patterns and academic achievement negatively.

Logically, behavioural problems often time result in psychological and emotional problems which give rise to worry, anxiety and depression especially when students fail academically. While some students might die in the process because they may fail to forgive themselves especially when they remember how they were lured into a particular life style that contribute to their academic failure. Similarly, there was a report of students in tertiary institutions in North central Nigeria particularly, Nasarawa State University who was killed by a ritualist after having canal knowledge of her. Again, Son and Yooncheong (2020) fund in their study that some students spent seven years in the university for four years course at Kogi State University. It is against this prevalence circumstances that this study was focused on investigating the influence of social demands on students' behavioural patterns and academic achievement in University in North Central Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The study was guided by the following objectives which were to:

- i. examine the influence of social demands on students' behavioural patterns in relation to substance abuse in the Universities in North-central Nigeria;

- ii. examine the level of academic achievement of students in the Universities in North-central Nigeria;
- iii. find out the influence of social demands on students' behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in the Universities in North-central Nigeria.
- iv. investigate the influence of social demands on students' academic achievement in the Universities in North central, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The researchers raised the following questions which guided the study.

1. What is the influence of social demands on students' behavioural pattern in relation to substance abuse in the Universities in North-central Nigeria?
2. What is the level of academic achievement of students in the Universities in North-central Nigeria?
3. What is the influence of social demands on students' behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in the Universities in North-central Nigeria?
4. What is the influence of social demands on students' academic achievement in the Universities in North central Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study and it was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H01: There is no significant difference between Federal and State Universities students on the influence of social demands and their behavioural patterns in relation to substance abuse in North-central Nigeria.

H02: There is no significant difference between male and female students on the influence of social demands and their behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in the University in North-central Nigeria.

H03: Federal and state universities students did not differ significantly on the influence of social demands on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive survey research design and ex-post facto. This survey research design involved collecting data from selected representatives of a population through research instrument and analyzing same to obtain results (Nworgu, 2016). On the other hand, ex-post facto is a type of non experimental study where the researcher analyzes existing data or condition after they have occurred.

Therefore, survey research design and ex-post facto method were ideal since the researchers were interested in subjecting the collected data to rigorous statistical analysis and hypotheses testing.

The population of this study was 25,115 which consist of all two hundred level students from three state universities and three Federal universities in North-central Nigeria.

The sample size for this study was 394 out of 25,115 students from six university which include both state and Federal Universities within the study area. This study adopted stratified random sampling technique in selecting the sample size from the population. The researcher considered the 5% of Yamane table of sample size (1967) as appropriate.

The instrument for this study was a self-structured questionnaire, titled Influence of Social Demands Questionnaire" (ISDQ). This instrument was divided into two sections A and B. Section A consisted demographic data of the respondents while section B consisted items on social demands. It had 14 items drawn on a 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1).

In order to establish the validity of the research instrument, the questionnaire was submitted to the two expert in the Department of Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education, University of Abuja for face, construct and content validity. After much corrections, constructive criticisms and observations on the content and the construct, it was therefore certified valid for the study.

The instrument was also subjected to a pilot test using 20 students of two hundred level (200) in University of Abuja. This was carried out in Faculty of Education, University of Abuja, that would not be

part in the main study. The reliability of the instrument was determined using test-retest method. After two weeks of the first administration of the test, the test was re-administered to the same group of students and the results from the two administrations were correlated using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC). The result therefore, yielded the reliability index of 0.71 which was considered reliable for the study.

The researchers and research assistants took permission from the Head of sampled Universities' Departments through the letter of introduction from the Department of Guidance and Counselling, University of Abuja. Thereafter, the researcher with the research assistants also applied for two hundred level students result particularly second semester result. The request was granted and for the purpose of identification, the result was coded along with the instrument using the last digit of students' registration number.

The respondents in this study was randomly picked from two departments such as Educational Foundation, Science Education and four programmes which include Educational Psychology, Social Studies, Environmental Education and Biology Education. Thereafter, the researchers and research assistants administered 420 copies of the instrument to students in the lecture hall and 394 were sieved based on the code. More so, the researcher and the research assistants briefed the respondents on the intention of the questionnaire and appeal for cooperation as well as assuring them of utmost confidentiality. The respondents were told that the information given shall be used strictly for research work. In situations where they did not understand some statement in the items, assistance were rendered by the researchers and research assistants by way of explaining the items on the questionnaire and allowing them to make their choices from the options provided.

The data for the study was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical tools. Descriptive tools of frequency count and percentages for students' personal information while, mean scores and standard deviation were used to answers the research questions. The testing of the hypotheses were done using inferential statistical tool of t-test. The hypotheses 1 to 2 were tested using a t-test because two groups were compared. While hypothesis 3 was tested using One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to determine differences between more than two groups.

For a decision rule was any statements that had 2.50 and above were considered as agreed while any statement below 2.50 was considered disagreed. The decision rule for all the hypotheses was that, any significant value that was 0.05 level of significance and above was accepted and any significance value that was below 0.05 level of significance was therefore rejected.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents based on Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	206	52.30
Female	188	47.70
Total	394	100.00

Table 1 showed the distribution of respondents based on gender. The number of male respondents was 206 (52.30%) while the female counterparts was 188 (47.70%). This means that there were more male genders in this study than female genders.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents based on Federal and State Universities

Federal/State	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Federal Universities	205	52.00
State Universities	189	48.00
Total	394	100.00

Table 2 showed the distribution of respondents based on Federal and State University. The number of Federal Universities respondents was 205 (52.00%) while the State Universities counterparts was 189 (48.00%). This means that there were more respondents from Federal Universities than respondents from State Universities.

Research Question One: What is the influence of social demands on students' behavioural pattern in relation to substance abuse in Universities in North-central Nigeria?

Table 3: Influence of social demands on students' behavioural pattern in relation to substance abuse in Universities in North-central, Nigeria.

N=394

S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
3.	I became addicted to drug through clubs	2.55	.996	Agreed
4.	I learn how to drink alcohol in a social gathering	2.91	1.071	Agreed
5.	I became a chain smoker in the name socialization	3.33	.691	Agreed
6.	Substance like marijuana make one reason well in the club	3.15	.824	Agreed
7.	I always feel intimidated if am not high among my groups.	3.16	.745	Agreed
8.	Desire to feel big has ruined my life which make me depend on drug.	3.22	.804	Agreed
Sectional Mean		3.05	0.855	

Table 3 showed the influence of social demands on students' behavioural patterns in relation to substance abuse in Universities in North-central Nigeria. The sectional mean score of respondents for social demand is 3.05, with a standard deviation of 0.855. This implies that the respondents agreed that there were some negative social demands in the Universities such as, substance abuse, alcohol and marijuana. While the standard deviation suggest the predominant nature of these social demands especially among students in the universities.

Research Question Two: What is the academic achievement of students in Universities in North-central Nigeria?

Table 4: The academic achievement of students in Universities in North-central Nigeria.

N=394

Courses	Minimum	Maximum	Average Score
EDU202	15.00	79.00	48.05
EDU206	14.00	67.00	46.23
GST202	17.00	72.00	47.10
GST222	40.00	88.00	64.52
Academic Achievement	30.50	66.25	51.26

Table 4 showed the academic achievement of students in Universities in North central Nigeria. The minimum score in EDU202 was 15.00, while the maximum score was 79.00 with the average score of 48.05. This means that the students score in EDU202 was below average. The students score in EDU206 has a minimum of 14.00, a maximum of 67.00 and an average score of 46.23. This also shows that the students score in EDU206 was below average.

The minimum students score in GST202 is 17.00, the maximum score 72.00 with average score of 47.10. This means that the students score in GST211 was below average. The minimum students score in GST222 was 40.00, the maximum score 88.00 with average score of 64.52. This means that the students score in GST222 was above average.

The academic achievement of students in Universities in North central Nigeria is minimum of 30.50, maximum of 66.25 and average of 51.26. The average score of 51.26 is within 50 midpoint which implies that overall academic performance of students was within average. To further answer the research questions, hypotheses were tested.

Research Question Three: What is the influence of social demands on students' behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in Universities in North-central Nigeria based on gender?

Table 5: Influence of social demands on students' behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in Universities in North-central, Nigeria.

		N=394			Decision	Table 5 showed the influence of social demands on students' behavioural
S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev.			
9.	I began stealing when I started going to club	3.13	.742	Agreed	Table 5 showed the influence of social demands on students' behavioural	
10.	I can do anything like begging and stealing	3.28	.721	Agreed		
11.	Stealing is normal in any social gathering	3.10	.749	Agreed		
12.	I can dump anybody just to celebrate birthday	3.26	.712	Agreed		
13.	I steal to live big always	3.27	.664	Agreed		
14.	Clubbing contributed to my stealing habit	3.21	.733	Agreed		
Sectional Mean		3.21	0.720			

patterns in relation to stealing in Universities in North-central, Nigeria. The table showed that the students agreed with all the items. The sectional mean score of respondents for social demands in relation to stealing is 3.21, with a standard deviation of 0.720. This implies that the respondents agreed that there is influence of social demands on students' behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in Universities in North central Nigeria. That many students steal to meet up their social status. The result of standard deviation clearly indicate the existence of this social phenomenon.

Test of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H01: There is no significant different between Federal and State Universities students on the influence of social demands and their behavioural patterns in relation to substance abuse in North-central, Nigeria.

Table 6: t-test on Difference between Federal and State Universities students on the influence of social demands and their behavioural patterns in relation to substance abuse in North-central, Nigeria

Location	Number	Mean	S.D.	t-value	df	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
Federal University	280	3.05	.458	-.257	392	.797	Accepted
State Univer.	114	3.06	.431				

Table 6 showed the significant different between Federal and State Universities students on the influence of social demands and their behavioural patterns in relation to substance abuse in North-central, Nigeria. With the significant values of .797 (more than the 0.05 level of significance), the hypothesis was, therefore accepted and concluded that Federal and State Universities respondents did not differ significantly in the influence of social demands and their behavioural patterns in relation to substance

abuse in North-central Nigeria, that both Federal and State Universities students were involved in substance abuse as a result of social demands.

H02: There is no significant difference between male and female students on the influence of social demands on their behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in University in North-central, Nigeria

Table 7: t-test on Difference between males and female students on the influence of social demands on their behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in University in North-central, Nigeria

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D.	t-value	df	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
Male	206	3.10	.429	1.972	392	.049	Rejected
Female	188	3.01	.469				

Table 7 showed the significant difference between males and female students on the influence of social demands on their behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in University in North-central, Nigeria. With the significant values of .049 (less than the 0.05 level of significance), the hypothesis that says that there is no different between males and female students on the influence of social demands on their behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in University in North-central, Nigeria was, therefore rejected and conclude that male and female respondents differ significantly in the influence of social demands on their behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in University in North-central, Nigeria that male students were more victims.

H06: Federal and state universities students did not differ significantly on the influence of social demands on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria.

Table 8: One-way ANOVA for the difference between Federal and state universities students on the influence of social demands on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria

FEDERAL AND STATE	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	.459	2	.039	.234	.641	Not Significant
Within Groups	48.895	391	.125			
Total	47.654	393				

The analysis in Table 8 was carried out to test the difference between Federal and state universities students on the influence of social demands on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria. With the significant values of 0.641 (more than the 0.05 level of significance), the hypothesis that says that Federal and state universities students did not differ significantly on the influence of social demands on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria is therefore, accepted and concluded that Federal and state universities students did not differ significantly on the influence of social demands on their academic achievement in North Central Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from research question one showed that, there were negative social demands in Universities in North-central Nigeria such as substance abuse, alcohol and marijuana. These practice appear to be a phenomena among various social setting and one of such setting was the University. As matter of fact, many people indulge in substance abuse in the name of social life. Again, the environmental factor is another strong force compelling students into negative social behaviour. This finding is in line with the assertion of Susanne, Mike and Norbert (2021) the authors said that, students with negative social behaviour influence those around them negatively regardless of location and it cut across even to their dressing. More so, the finding is also in line with the observation of Manjur, Raisa Ahmed and Abdalla (2017) they reported that, 57% of university students were addicted to social media while 59% of them reported that social media had affected their social interactions negatively and made them to be addicted

to drug especially students in the university. In this wise, social forces could be regarded as magnetic and when come in contact, it can influence anyone negatively especially for those who allow it.

It was found from research question two that, the academic achievement of students in Universities in North-central Nigeria is within average. There is no doubt that, students who are suppose to be first class grade could drop down as a result of many circumstances like social demands, personal traits, and peer pressure. This findings is similar to the finding of Ajibade (2016) who found that, peer group influences the academic performance of students averagely. In like manner, the findings is also in line with the opinion of Chebet, (2018), who asserted that peer group members who perform averagely had positive influence on their academic performance in secondary schools. It was therefore concluded that, students' academic performance were average despite the influence of social demands. Therefore, some students who were suppose to be first class students end up becoming an average students due to influence of negative social demands,

The findings from research questions three indicated that social demands influence students' behavioural patterns in terms of stealing, that they steal to meet up their social status. The desire to be relevant socially had push many people particularly students into negative social behaviour. Some go as far as stealing, scams, pick pocket just to remain relevant physically within their social class. Often time, their social relevant is define by the type of phone, shoes, wear and necklace one put on per time. In view of the above, Alams, Muhammed and Sajja (2018), in their study, found that negative social behaviour that characterized the students were indecent dressing, stealing and yahoo yahoo. In like manner, filade (2019) found that, peer group contributed to students' negative social behaviour such as substance abuse, cultism, yahoo yahoo and stealing. In addition, Wasiu and Temilade (2021), in their study, they discovered that, gang negative social behaviour was prevalent among 20.8% of the JSS3 students especially in the area of stealing, 29.0% of the SS1 students and 17.2% of the SS2 students. It can be said that, negative social forces had great influence on students' behaviour negatively. The high level of this influence informed the similarities of this study with the previous studies.

It was found from hypotheses one that Federal and State Universities students do not differ significantly in the influence of social demands on their behavioural pattern in relation to substance abuse in North central Nigeria. Human by nature always want to have a taste of almost everything include substance abuse. When this desire is not put into checked, the individual involved may abuse anything that comes on their way like substance. This finding is similar the study of filade (2019), he found that, male students were often intentional in their smoking behaviour and abuse of other substance irrespective of Federal and State Universities. In this present age, some students are prone to negative influence everywhere irrespective of Universities and this influence could comes through social media, physical social forum like event centers and social environment. But the ability to say no to any negative social pressure depends on the will power of the individual involved.

It was revealed from hypotheses two that, male and female students differ significantly in the influence of social demands on students' behavioural patterns in relation to stealing in University in North central Nigeria, that male students were more victims. The development of negative social behaviour has become a phenomenon in our contemporary society especially among University students. This negative behaviour has painted our society with the bad image. This findings is inline with the opinion of Manjur, Raisa, Ahmed and Abdalla (2017) they found that, male and female differ significantly in the influence of social media used and its effect on their behaviour in relation to stealing, drug abuse and addiction but male students are more victims.

The findings from hypotheses three revealed that, social demands influence both Federal and State Universities students' academic achievement negatively. It has been said that social demands were powerful force influences one's choice and ultimately interrupt one's activities like studies. It is often believed that, anything that consume one's time unconsciously can make a mark on a plan activities. Although, some students can perform better academically in the face of social demands due to inherent tendency of an individual. This finding is similar to that of Fadare, Zarma, Fadare, Bademosi and Amanum (2021) they found that, all the tested hypotheses were negative in relation to academic performance due to clubbing.

CONCLUSION

From the findings of the study, it was concluded that, there were negative social demands in Universities in North-central Nigeria, such as substance abuse, alcohol and marijuana. It was also concluded that, the overall academic performance of students were within average. It was further further concluded that, social demands affects students negatively on the aspect of stealing. While the influence on students' behavioural patterns do not differ significantly in respect to Federal and State Universities, gender, as regards to substance abuse and stealing in North-central, Nigeria. It was finally concluded that, social demands influence both Federal and State Universities students' academic achievement negatively.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendation were made from the findings of this study;

1. Educators at all level should use every opportunity to educate the students about the negative effects of social demands especially on substance abuse
2. Parents, teachers and other stakeholders should always emphasize and educate the students on the importance of academic achievement in relation to world of work.
3. Guidance counsellor's should organize periodic guidance programme on maladaptive behaviour like stealing and other negative social vices especially among the university students.

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